

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE EFFECT OF ENVIRONMENTAL PARAMETERS ON THE REACTANCE PARAMETER OF THE OVERHEAD POWER TRANSMISSION LINE WITH THE UNBUNDLED PHASE

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ABSTRACT

Changes in environmental parameters (temperature, atmospheric pressure, air humidity, wind speed, solar radiation etc.) cause changes in the electrical parameters of electrical power equipment. However, in most cases, this effect is accounted for solely by taking into account the temperature dependence of the active resistance, which varies in proportion to the temperature coefficient of resistance of the conductor material and a temperature by itself.

At the same time, changes in environmental parameters also affect other electrical parameters of electrical power equipment – reactance, conductance and susceptance. The corresponding dependencies are less obvious and, in terms of their relative impact on parameter values, less significant than the dependence of resistance on temperature. However, in case of the wide range of variation in environmental parameters, such an effect may be significant for technical or economic calculations.

This paper examines the influence of environmental parameters of temperature, atmospheric pressure and air humidity on the reactive resistance of an overhead power transmission line with an unbundled phase.

Keywords: power transmission line, reactance, temperature, atmospheric pressure, air humidity.

Introduction

The modern power industry is a complex technical system, the reliability and efficiency of which depend to a large extent on the proper consideration of the operating conditions of the equipment. One of the key factors influencing the operation of power facilities is environmental conditions. Air temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, solar radiation, ice, atmospheric pollution and other natural factors can significantly alter the electrical characteristics of equipment, affecting its service life, reliability and operational safety. This is precisely why taking the impact of the environment into account is an integral part of the design, operation and modernisation of power systems.

Of all the environmental parameters, temperature is the most significant factor affecting the electrical characteristics of electrical power equipment. It is well known that the electrical resistance of conductive materials increases with rising temperature in proportion to the temperature coefficient of resistance [1]:

$$R_{T_2} = R_{T_1} \cdot (1 + \alpha \cdot (T_2 - T_1)), \quad (1)$$

where:

R_{T_1} – the DC resistance at temperature T_1 ;

R_{T_2} – the DC resistance at temperature T_2 ;

α – the temperature coefficient of electrical resistance at temperature T_1 .

Consequently (1), as the ambient temperature rises, active power losses increase in power transmission lines, substation busbars, cables and the windings of electrical machines.

The temperature changes also affect the mechanical properties of conductors. For example, the heating of overhead power line conductors causes them to elongate and increases sag, which can lead to a breach of standard dimensions and the occurrence of emergency situations [2]. In transformers, temperature determines

the permissible load, dictates the rate of insulation ageing and the overall service life of the equipment [3].

The level of humidity determines the rate at which conductive films form on the surfaces of insulators and electrical equipment, thereby increasing leakage currents and the likelihood of surface breakdown of the insulation. A combination of high humidity with surface contamination from dust or industrial emissions is particularly dangerous, as under such conditions the electrical strength of the insulation is significantly reduced and the risk of emergency outages increases.

Wind speed also has a significant impact on the operation of electrical power equipment. On the one hand, wind improves the cooling of conductors, transformers and other network components, thereby increasing their capacity. On the other hand, strong winds place additional mechanical stress on pylons, cables and insulators. Under certain conditions, dangerous vibrations and oscillations of the cables may occur, which accelerate their wear and tear and increase the probability of damage.

Solar radiation is another significant factor influencing the electrical parameters of power equipment. Under the influence of solar radiation, the surface temperature of cables and equipment can significantly exceed the ambient air temperature. This affects the thermal operating conditions of electrical installations, alters the electrical resistance of conductors and limits permissible current loads. This is precisely why the intensity of solar radiation must be taken into account when calculating the capacity of overhead power lines.

Thus, environmental parameters have a direct impact on the electrical, thermal and mechanical characteristics of electrical power equipment. Ignoring this impact can lead to design errors, equipment overload, accelerated ageing of insulation and the occurrence of

emergencies. Therefore, taking environmental parameters into account is a necessary prerequisite for ensuring the efficient, safe and reliable operation of modern power systems.

For a number of electrical parameters of power equipment, the effect of changes in environmental conditions is negligible almost negligible. However, in case of the wide range of variation in environmental parameters, such an effect may be significant for technical or economic calculations. One such parameter is the reactance of power transmission lines, the values of which can also be expressed as a function of environmental parameters.

Calculation of the reactance of an overhead power line transmission with an unsplit phase with an unbundled phase

It is known that the reactance per length of an overhead power line with an unbundled phase can be determined as follows [4]:

Figure 1. The spatial arrangement of the phases of an overhead power transmission line with the unbundled phase

The effect of temperature on the reactance of an overhead power line with an unbundled phase

The magnetic constant, the voltage frequency and the root-mean-square distance between the phases of the overhead power line, which are included in (2), are independent of the ambient temperature.

The dependence of a conductor material's relative magnetic permeability on temperature is determined by the type of material.

For copper, which is diamagnetic, the relative magnetic permeability is practically independent of temperature and, within the temperature range of $-50^{\circ}\text{C} \dots +70^{\circ}\text{C}$ (where $+70^{\circ}\text{C}$ is the highest permissible temperature of the copper wire in the continuous steady state condition), can be regarded as a constant to an accuracy less than 10^{-7} ($\mu_{\text{Cu}}=0,999992$).

For aluminium, which is paramagnetic, the temperature dependence of the relative magnetic permeability is described by Curie's law:

$$\mu_r(T) = 1 + \frac{C}{T}, \quad (4)$$

where:

C – Curie's constant, which is independent of the ambient temperature;

T – absolute temperature.

If considering $\mu_{r\text{Al}}(+20^{\circ}\text{C})=1,0000220$ and taking (4) into account then for the temperature range of $-50^{\circ}\text{C} \dots +70^{\circ}\text{C}$ (where -50°C approximately equal to the lowest temperature in Europe and $+70^{\circ}\text{C}$ is the highest permissible temperature of the aluminium and

$$x_0 = \mu_0 \cdot f \cdot \left(\ln \left(\frac{2 \cdot D_{GM}}{d_w} \right) + \frac{\mu_r}{4} \right), \quad (2)$$

where:

μ_0 – vacuum permeability ($\mu_0 \approx 4\pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ H/m);

f – voltage frequency;

μ_r – relative permeability of the power transmission wires material;

d_w – outer diameter of the power transmission wires;

D_{GM} – geometric mean distance between the phases of the power transmission line, which can be calculated as:

$$D_{GM} = \sqrt[3]{D_{1-2} \cdot D_{2-3} \cdot D_{3-1}}, \quad (3)$$

where:

$D_{1-2}, D_{2-3}, D_{3-1}$ – distances between the axis of the power transmission line phases as given on Fig. 1.

steel-aluminium wires in the continuous steady state condition) can be obtained $\mu_{r\text{Al}}(-50^{\circ}\text{C})=1,0000289$ and $\mu_{r\text{Al}}(+70^{\circ}\text{C})=1,0000188$.

The absolute change of the aluminium relative permeability in the temperature range of $-50^{\circ}\text{C} \dots +70^{\circ}\text{C}$ is 10^{-5} or 0,001%.

For the steel-aluminium wires the dependence of a conductor material's relative magnetic permeability on temperature is more complicated because of steel core influence. In this case total magnetic permeability of the steel-aluminium wire μ_{rw} can be calculated as follows:

$$\mu_{rw} = \mu_{r\text{Al}} \cdot \left(\frac{I_{\text{Al}}}{I} \right)^2 + \mu_{r\text{St}} \cdot \left(\frac{I_{\text{St}}}{I} \right)^2, \quad (5)$$

where:

$\mu_{r\text{St}}$ – relative permeability of steel;

I_{Al} – current flowing through the aluminium part of the wire;

I_{St} – current flowing through the steel part of the wire;

I – total current flowing through the wire.

For steel, the relative magnetic permeability is a function of the magnetic flux density, the magnetic field strength and the temperature; therefore, its value is usually determined as follows:

$$\mu_{r\text{St}}(T) = \frac{B(T)}{\mu_0 \cdot H(T)}, \quad (6)$$

where:

$B(T)$ – functional dependence of magnetic induction on temperature;

$H(T)$ – functional dependence of the magnetic field strength on temperature.

As a rule, the value of the ratio $B(T)/H(T)$ is determined from the $B(H)$ graphs plotted for a certain temperature:

$$\mu_{r\ St}(T) = \frac{B(T)}{\mu_0 \cdot H(T)}, \quad (6)$$

For the simplified calculations the relationship between the relative magnetic permeability of steel and temperature can be expressed as:

$$\mu_{r\ St}(T) = \mu_{r\ St + 20^\circ C} \cdot (1 - 0,002 \cdot \Delta T), \quad (7)$$

where:

$\mu_{r\ St + 20^\circ C}$ – steel relative magnetic permeability at a temperature of $+20^\circ C$;

ΔT – the temperature difference between the strand temperature T and $20^\circ C$:

$$\Delta T = T - 20^\circ C. \quad (8)$$

Changes in ambient temperature and the current load on the wire cause the wire's diameter to change. For each strand in the wire assembly, the change in strand diameter as a function of temperature $d(T)$ can be determined as:

$$d(T) = d_{+20^\circ C} \cdot (1 + \alpha \cdot \Delta T), \quad (9)$$

where:

$d_{+20^\circ C}$ – strand diameter at a temperature of $+20^\circ C$;

α – the coefficient of linear thermal expansion of the strand material (for aluminium $\alpha=23 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ C^{-1}$ [5], for copper $\alpha=17 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ C^{-1}$, for steel $\alpha=12 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ C^{-1}$).

The number and diameter of the strands in the construction of copper, aluminium and steel-aluminium cables can be determined in accordance with standard [5].

The effect of atmospheric pressure and air humidity on the reactance of an overhead power line with an unbundled phase

Atmospheric pressure and humidity levels have no direct effect on the components of (2).

At the same time, changes in air humidity lead to changes in the heat dissipation process from the conductor, whilst changes in atmospheric pressure lead to changes in the convection process, which affect the conductor's temperature; this, in turn, affects the value of μ_r .

A change in the temperature of the conductor causes a change in the mechanical tension within it, which leads to a slight change in the value due to a change in the domain structure of the steel core of the steel-aluminium conductor. At the same time, these effects are extremely weak, which means they can be disregarded over a wide range of variations in relative humidity and atmospheric pressure.

Results of calculations of changes in the reactance of an overhead power line due to changes of the environmental parameters

A calculation was carried out to determine the change in the reactance per 1 km of an overhead power line in the event of changes in environmental parameters for an overhead line constructed using PM110-1F type pylons (Fig. 2), for copper, aluminium and steel-aluminium wires at temperatures of $-50^\circ C$, $+20^\circ C$ and $+70^\circ C$. The results of the calculations are given in Table 1.

Table 1.

Results of calculations of the reactance per 1 km of an overhead power line based on different types of supports and conductors at various temperatures

Wire type [5]	Material	Reactance per 1 km X , Ohm, for temperature, $^\circ C$		
		-50	+20	+70
A 120	aluminum	0,4389	0,4389	0,4388
M 120	copper	0,4390	0,4389	0,4389
AC 120/19	aluminum-steel	0.4426	0,4403	0,4394

Figure 2. PM110-1F-type pylon diagram

Conclusions

It has been established that environmental parameters influence the reactance of an overhead power transmission line. The greatest influence comes from changes in ambient temperature, which affect both the relative magnetic permeability of the conductor material and the conductor's diameter. However, for overhead power transmission lines with aluminium and copper wires within the temperature range of $-50^{\circ}\text{C} \dots +70^{\circ}\text{C}$, this effect is negligibly small, whilst temperature changes have the greatest impact on the reactance of overhead power transmission lines with aluminium-steel wires.

References

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